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Thermal Response and Failure Mode Evaluation of a Dry-Type Transformer

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Abstract

In this work, the safe working limits of a 10 kVA dry-type transformer with H-class insulation are determined by modeling its thermal response in different scenarios using numerical simulations (CFD). A numerical model of the heat transfer from the transformer to its surroundings by natural convection has been developed. Firstly, a steady regime with the transformer working at full load at an ambient temperature of 300 K is studied in order to gain insight into the heat transmission mechanisms. Then, a series of 32 steady simulations with different load and ambient conditions is performed to characterize insulation aging due to overheating. Finally, a second group of 9 transient simulations is employed to assess the transformer failure time under an overload situation. The results show a coupling between the thermal and flow fields. The hot spot temperatures obtained by the model are consistent with previous experimental observations and the time that the transformer resists an overload has been calculated. The results obtained allow the prediction of the thermal behavior of a transformer under different scenarios, reducing the need for instrumentation, as well as experimental tests which result in the loss of the testing transformer.

Keywords: numerical analysis; electrothermal effects; power transformer losses; power transformer insulation; failure analysis.

Nomenclature

α	Steinmetz equation exponent, thermal expansion coefficient [1/K]
β	coefficient for the equation of state for air, air volumetric expansion coefficient [1/K]
\dot{Q}	rate of heat transfer [W]
\dot{Q}_{in}	heat entering the system [W]

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\dot{W}_{out}	work done by the system [W]
γ	coefficient for the equation of state for air
μ	dynamic viscosity [Pa · s]
ν	air kinematic viscosity [m ² /s]
ρ	density [kg/m ³]
ρ_{∞}	ambient air density [kg/m ³]
ρ_{Cu}	copper resistivity [Ωm]
σ	electrical conductivity [$\Omega^{-1}m^{-1}$]
A	coefficient for the equation of state for air, constant of life expectancy equation for a transformer, heat transfer area [m ²]
a	magnetic sheet thickness [m]
B	coefficient for the equation of state for air, constant of life expectancy equation for a transformer
B_m	magnetic induction field [T]
C_P	specific heat [J/kg · K]
<i>CFD</i>	Computational Fluid Dynamics
f	force [N], transformer working frequency [Hz]
<i>FEM</i>	Finite Element Method
g	gravity acceleration [m/s ²]
Gr	Grashof number
h	heat transfer coefficient [W/m ² · K], height [m], specific enthalpy [J/kg]
H_{crit}	critical transformer height (transition to turbulent) [m]
I	current intensity [A]
I_{Φ}	phase intensity [A]
I_R	intensity ratio (overload/nominal intensity)
k	thermal conductivity [W/m · K]
k_F	Foucault losses constant
k_H	Steinmetz equation constant
L	characteristic length of the transformer [m], wire length [m]

m	mass [kg]
Nu	Nusselt number
p	pressure [Pa]
P_{Cu}	copper losses [W/m^3]
Pr	Prandtl number
R	wire resistance [Ω]
S	conductor wire section [m^2], transformer power [VA]
S_h	source term [W/m^3]
T	temperature [K, °C]
t	time [s]
t_F	failure time of the transformer insulation [s, h]
t_L	insulation life expectancy [s, h]
T_∞	ambient temperature [K]
T_{HS}	hot spot temperature [K]
u	horizontal velocity [m/s], specific internal energy [J/kg]
v	vertical velocity [m/s]
V_L	line tension [V]
x	horizontal position [m]
y	vertical position [m]

1. Introduction

Transformers prevail as a fundamental element of current electric grid systems, in which AC power is transported over long distances from power plants to urban and rural areas. Voltage boosters are placed at the output of power plant alternators (15-30 kV) to increase the voltage up to adequate transport levels (132/230/400V), while voltage reducers are placed to lower the voltage down to the required values for energy distribution and consumption.

Due to the high dependence of safety critical systems on power electronics, an unpredicted failure in a power electronic system could cause a fatal accident or, in the best scenario, a high penalty cost. Transformers are high-cost equipment and a critical part of electric power systems, so it is important to guarantee their proper functioning: the study of their behavior and the use of specific protection for them is more than justified.

Among all transformers, dry-type transformers are worth highlighting. They do not propagate fire, they are self-extinguishing and they do not spill flammable or contaminant materials in the case of failure. Hence, they are currently the safest and most reliable transformers for low voltage applications, being suitable for installation in places with high safety requirements such as interior locals, public buildings, hospitals, shopping centers and mines. The most critical part of a dry-type transformer is the insulation, bound to fail as a result of thermal aging. As reported by Sokolov [1], winding insulation failure is responsible for almost 30 % of transformer failures. The main originating cause of thermal aging is the electric overload of the transformer, which leads to system overheating and contributes to a continuous reduction in the transformer lifespan. Besides, there is a threshold temperature which suddenly renders the transformer useless.

Due to the great impact of the transformer temperature on its durability, the estimation of the temperature evolution of the transformer under different conditions is vital to increase its useful life. There are some models, based on equivalent electrical circuits, which predict the thermal response of oil-type transformers (Swift, Molinski and Lehn [2], Susa and Nordman [3], Najafi and Iskender [4]). Similar models were presented by Ghareh and Sepahi [5] and Nabhani, Hodgson and Warnakulasuriya [6] for dry-type transformers. However, all of these models require an adjustment with experimental correction factors. Some attempts, as the one performed by Najafi and Iskender [7], have been made with FEM techniques to provide a better insight into the core magnetic flux density, but the thermal models employed are similar to the previous ones. An estimation of the transformer temperature evolution is given by these models, but it would be desirable to predict the evolution of the thermal and surrounding fluid fields, as well as the heat transmission mechanisms, in order to achieve a better understanding and characterization of the system. Predictive numerical models represent an inexpensive tool for the evaluation of multiple scenarios [8] [9] [10], helping to determine the most adequate maintenance plans. Besides, modifications and optimizations can be simulated before proceeding to experimental tests. Apart from reducing the amount of experimental tests required, numerical simulations enrich the analysis by providing a complete picture of the fluid flow and heat transmission mechanisms. This information may complement experimental results such as the ones from Patel, Parekh and Upadhyay [11], who compared experimentally the performance of oil and a magnetic fluid used as transformer coolants.

In this work, the safe working limits of a 10 kVA dry-type transformer with H-class insulation have been analyzed. The study has been performed using the CFD software Fluent[®], developing a total of 41 simulations. A first group of 32 simulations studies the natural loss of the transformer lifespan under steady conditions for 8 different load regimes and 4 ambient temperatures. The second group of simulations has been used to determine the failure time of the transformer for 9 different overload intensities, starting from steady conditions.

Table 1: Technical Specifications of the Transformer

Power	10 kVA
Transformation ratio	1:1
Primary/Secondary Voltage	400/400 V
Induction field	1 T
Insulation class	H
Max. temperature resisted by insulation	180/250°C (steady/transient)
Winding material	3 mm magnet wire
Winding arrangement	Alternate
Turns of the primary winding	172 (4 discs x 43 turns/disc)
Turns of the secondary winding	171 (3 discs x 57 turns/disc)
Magnetic sheets thickness	0.5 mm
Number of sheet layers	160
Limb and yoke section	80 mm x 80 mm

Figure 1: Transformer to be modeled.

2. Methodology

The aim of this study is the prediction of the safe working limits of a 10 kVA dry-type transformer with H-class insulation. To achieve this purpose, the thermal behavior of the transformer under different scenarios has been determined using numerical simulations. The characteristics of the transformer are collected in Table 1. A picture of the transformer is provided in Fig. 1.

2.1. Relevant laws and hypotheses for the development of the numerical model

The most relevant laws and hypotheses for the development of the numerical model are described below. The assumptions performed will be validated afterwards, throughout the paper.

1. Matter conservation laws must be observed, so mass, momentum and energy are to be conserved [12]:

- Continuity equation

$$\frac{Dm}{Dt} = 0 \quad (1)$$

- Momentum equation

$$\frac{D(mv)}{Dt} = \sum f \quad (2)$$

- Energy equation

$$\frac{D}{Dt} \left[m \left(u + \frac{1}{2}v^2 - gh \right) \right] = \dot{Q}_{in} - \dot{W}_{out} \quad (3)$$

2. The thermophysical properties of solid materials are considered constant.
3. The thermophysical properties of the surrounding air are also considered constant, except for density, which is modelled as a polynomial function of the temperature (expressed in K):

$$\rho(T) = 2.711 - 0.006711 T + 5.36410^{-6} T^2 \left[\frac{kg}{m^3} \right] \quad (4)$$

4. The magnetic core and the winding turns act as heat sources.
5. Temperatures are low enough to neglect heat transfer by radiation.
6. Heat transfer between the transformer and its surroundings is produced exclusively by natural convection.
7. The air enclosed in the magnetic core has the same properties as the surrounding air, although the simulations in that region considered only heat conduction. It was found that enabling natural convection in this zone had a negligible effect in the final state of the transformer, so only heat conduction was introduced for simplicity.
8. Turbulence effects are neglected, so the air flow is considered as laminar.

2.2. Model geometry, boundary conditions and mesh generation

The simulations have been performed in a 2D section taken in the middle of the transformer, assuming that heat transfer occurs mainly transversally to the transformer walls. This simplification makes the results more conservative due to the air blockage in the center of the transformer, so the model remains valid for the purpose of this study: the determination of the safe working limits of the transformer, even when a slight underestimation of the threshold temperature

Figure 2: Numerical model generated in Gambit[®], with a magnification of the primary and secondary windings.

could happen.

The whole simulation domain generated in Gambit[®], with the corresponding materials, may be seen in Fig. 2. The transformer is symmetric from the geometrical and thermal point of view. Therefore, only half of the transformer-ambient domain has been simulated.

The boundary conditions applied to the domain may be recognized in Fig. 3. The left boundary of the domain is defined in Fluent[®] as a “SYMMETRY” boundary, as there is neither flow nor heat transfer across it. The right boundary of the domain is far enough from the transformer in order not to be affected by its effects. The fluid is quiescent, as the whole zone is at the same ambient temperature and natural convection predominates. Therefore, it is modeled as a “WALL” boundary, with zero air velocity (no-slip condition) and a constant ambient temperature. The upper and lower boundaries of the domain must allow air circulation from the bottom (“PRESSURE INLET”) to the top (“PRESSURE OUTLET”) of the domain. Both are at atmospheric pressure, and the flow crosses the boundary perpendicularly.

The domain has been discretized in a total of 50,177 triangular cells of different sizes (non-structured mesh), with a size ratio of 100 between the largest and the smallest cell. The smallest cells have been placed at the vertical surface of the transformer in contact with air, the region where the higher gradients of flow and thermophysical properties are expected to be found. As shown in Fig. 4, the cell size increases smoothly from this zone.

2.3. Thermophysical properties of the materials present in the model

Table 2 summarizes the thermophysical properties of the materials that constitute the transformer, as well as the air properties for the whole domain: thermal conductivity, specific heat and density. The air viscosity is considered to be $1.7894 \cdot 10^{-5}$ kg/(m·s). In the case that the temperature-dependency of materials would like to be considered, this may be done by changing directly the material

Figure 3: Domain zones and boundary conditions applied.

Figure 4: a) Detail of the mesh of the simulation domain. b) Mesh of a primary winding, divided into the transformer solid zone (top) and air zone (bottom).

definitions. A simulation was performed setting temperature-dependent properties, finding that the temperature increased around 7 K (a variation of 1.5%) with respect to the baseline simulation. Although this is a marginal increment, the thermal properties of all solid and fluid materials as a function of temperature could be introduced in the model if a more precise approach were desired.

2.4. Heat transfer analysis

The analysis of heat transfer in the domain comprises the three following parts: heat sources, heat transfer by conduction and heat transfer by convection.

2.4.1. Heat sources

When the transformer is working, variable and fixed energy losses arise. Variable losses are originated in copper, whereas fixed losses are originated in iron. Copper losses are induced by the electrical currents in the transformer windings due to Joule effect [13]:

$$P_{Cu} [W] = RI^2 = \frac{\rho_{Cu}L}{S} I^2 \rightarrow P_{Cu} \left[\frac{W}{m^3} \right] = \frac{\rho_{Cu}}{S^2} I^2 \quad (5)$$

Table 2: Thermophysical properties of the model materials

Ref. in Fig. 3	Material	Thermal conductivity [W/(m·K)]	Specific heat [J/(kg·K)]	Density [kg/m ³]
1	Cross-linked polyethylene (XLPE)	2	385	1380
2	Mylar (PET)	0.24	1000	1370
3, 4	Copper	399	385	8700
5	Polyurethane (enamel)	0.2	1700	2000
6	Silicon steel	28	501.6	7650
7	Air	0.0242	1006.43	= f(T)

where R is the wire electrical resistance, ρ is copper electrical resistivity, S and L are the wire section and length and I is the current intensity circulating through the windings. Iron losses arise in the magnetic core, where energy is converted from electric to magnetic and vice versa. The efficiency of these conversions is not perfect, so part of the inlet energy is lost as heat. This loss can be ascribed to two causes:

- Hysteresis behavior of the material (hysteresis losses): an experimental correlation, known as the Steinmetz equation and presented in [14], is often used to determine the hysteresis losses:

$$P_H \left[\frac{W}{m^3} \right] = k_H f B_m^\alpha \quad (6)$$

The values of k_H (Steinmetz coefficient) and α (Steinmetz exponent) depend on the ferromagnetic core nature. α varies between 1.5 and 2.5, being $\alpha = 1.6$ a typical value, while k_H varies between 100 and 200 for silicon steel. f is the transformer working frequency and B_m is the induction field.

- Eddy currents induced in the core (Foucault currents): the power dissipated by these currents observes the following law [13]:

$$P_F \left[\frac{W}{m^3} \right] = k_F f^2 B_m^2 a^2 \sigma \quad (7)$$

where a is the magnetic sheet thickness, σ the conductivity of the magnetic core, f the transformer working frequency and $k_F = \pi^2/6$.

The power dissipated per unit volume due to each of these three phenomena, when the transformer is working at full load, is collected in Table 3. It is known

Table 3: Heat Sources in the Transformer Working at Full Load

Phenomenon	Transformer zone	Power per unit volume [W/m ²]
Joule effect losses	Turns	70880
Hysteresis losses	Core	1900
Foucault current losses	Core	1800

that the magnetic flux density is unevenly distributed in the transformer core, with flux transfer occurring in a very narrow region of 1 mm before and after air gaps [15]. Far from those gaps, the flux density level is identical in all sheets and equal to the value of the core induction [16]. Nevertheless, due to the small extent of the region in which unevenness arises, the distribution of the heat source may be assumed as even without significant loss of accuracy (the aim of this work is to assess transformer life due to thermal effects and not the precise distribution of magnetic fields inside it).

2.4.2. Heat conduction

Heat conduction dominates heat transmission inside the transformer. As the transformer is modeled as a solid, there is no fluid flow and it is only necessary to solve the unsteady Poisson equation for heat transfer [12]:

$$\frac{d}{dt}(\rho h) = \nabla \cdot (k \nabla T) + S_h \quad (8)$$

where h is the enthalpy, k is the material conductivity and S_h is a volumetric heat source representing the heat generated in the turns and the magnetic core of the transformer.

2.4.3. Natural convection

The heat generated inside the transformer is removed by the surrounding air in contact with its external surfaces by natural convection. The air flow is driven by buoyancy forces due to the density variation between adjacent fluid layers. Mathematically speaking, the velocity field is coupled to the temperature field, as the air density depends on the temperature. This dependence may be expressed as follows:

$$\rho = \rho_\infty \left[1 - \beta (T - T_\infty) + \gamma (T - T_\infty)^2 \right] \quad (9)$$

where ρ_∞ is the air density at a point far away from the transformer, with β and γ as constants. This leads to reformulate the equation of state, resulting in the following buoyancy forces term:

$$(\rho_\infty - \rho) g = \rho_\infty g \left[A (T - T_\infty) - B (T - T_\infty)^2 \right] \quad (10)$$

where A and B are constants. This expression, similar to the Boussinesq approximation [12], generates the coupling between the thermal and velocity fields and may be introduced in the Navier-Stokes y-momentum equation to simplify the solving process. If the flow were isothermal ($T = T_\infty$), the driving forces would cancel throughout the whole domain and no flow would exist ($u = v = 0$). On the other hand, when the fluid is being heated by the transformer, this volumetric term ($\rho_\infty - \rho$) acquires a finite value, and so do the velocities. With all the aforementioned simplifications, the following system of Navier-Stokes equations is applied in Fluent[®] for the whole fluid domain [17],[18]:

- Continuity equation

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (11)$$

- x-momentum equation

$$u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} + \nu \nabla^2 u \quad (12)$$

- y-momentum equation

$$u \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = g \left[A(T - T_\infty) - B(T - T_\infty)^2 \right] + \nu \nabla^2 v \quad (13)$$

- Energy equation

$$u \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = \alpha \nabla^2 T \quad (14)$$

In order to couple the velocity and pressure fields, the SIMPLE algorithm has been employed to correct the pressure values [17].

2.5. Validation of results

Before studying the transformer failure modes, the simulation must be validated. With the purpose of verifying the natural convection hypothesis, the behavior of a transformer working at full load and at an ambient temperature of 300 K has been simulated. Then, an analysis of natural convection over the transformer vertical surface at a constant temperature has been executed via integral methods. Finally, a comparison between the mean temperature of the transformer vertical surface obtained by the two procedures has been performed. The integral analysis of natural convection over a vertical surface is performed using experimental correlations based on non-dimensional numbers [19], [20]:

$$Pr = \frac{C_P \mu}{k} \quad \text{Prandtl number} \quad (15)$$

$$Gr = \frac{g \beta (T - T_\infty) L^3}{\nu^2} \quad \text{Grashof number} \quad (16)$$

$$Nu = 0.15 (Gr \cdot Pr)^{1/3} \quad \text{Nusselt number} \quad (17)$$

$$h = \frac{Nu \cdot k}{L} \quad \text{Heat transfer coefficient} \quad (18)$$

With the value of the heat transfer coefficient, when the heat flux is known, the value of the surface temperature can be obtained with the following equation:

$$T = T_{\infty} + \frac{\dot{Q}}{hA} \quad (19)$$

Another necessary step to validate the model is the heat balance verification: the heat generated inside the transformer domain due to the heat sources must equal the heat dissipated due to natural convection. Besides, the hypothesis of neglecting turbulence effects must be confirmed. To validate this assumption, it must be verified that the Grashof number for the transformer vertical surface remains under the critical value that marks transition to turbulent flow, 10^9 . This value corresponds to a critical transformer height: if the actual height of the transformer vertical does not exceed this critical height, it can be assumed that the boundary layer will be laminar:

$$H_{crit} = \sqrt[3]{\frac{10^9 \mu^2}{g\beta\Delta T\rho_{\infty}\rho}} \geq H_{transformer} \quad (20)$$

2.6. Characterization of insulation aging

The IEEE Std 57.96-1989 [21] suggests that the insulation life expectancy of a dry-type transformer depends on its internal maximum temperature (hot spot temperature), following a relationship based on the Arrhenius reaction rate theory:

$$\ln(t_L) = B/T_{HS} + A \quad (21)$$

where t_L is the lifetime in hours, T_{HS} is the transformer hot spot temperature in K and A and B are experimentally determined constants. For an H-class insulation (maximum allowed temperature of 180°C), the values of A and B are -19.671 and 14,222 respectively. With this relationship, it is possible to predict the lifespan of the transformer as a function of the load regime and ambient temperature. Such integration of loading conditions into the failure model has been already exposed by Awadallah, Milanović and Jarman [22] or Najdenkosk, Rafajlovski and Dimcev [23]. In order to perform this integration, the value of the current circulating through each transformer phase I_{Φ} must be obtained. Knowing that the line tension V_L is 400 V, the current intensity may be calculated from the transformer power (S) equation [13]:

$$S = \sqrt{3}V_L I_{\Phi} \quad (22)$$

The value of the transformer current intensity is then used to estimate the copper losses using Equation 5. These losses are converted into a heat source in the winding turns for the simulations.

By the completion of simulations of the transformer behavior with different load regimes and ambient temperatures, an equation of the type $T_{HS} = f(S, T_{\infty})$ is sought. The different working power values evaluated range from 6 to 13 kVA in intervals of 1 KVA, while the ambient temperature values are 290, 300, 310

and 320 K. These values are the most representative of the transformer working range and the most probable temperatures in most of the geographical locations. Altogether, 32 cases were simulated, with each simulation lasting for 3 hours of CPU time.

2.7. Characterization of the thermal field variation when an overload is produced

One of the aims of this work is the calculation of the maximum time that a transformer can resist an overload. For this particular case, the threshold temperature that the transformer insulation is able to withstand is 250°C. With the purpose of determining the maximum working time under an overload condition, simulations in 9 different scenarios with an overload 2 to 10 times higher than the transformer nominal current intensity have been performed. It has been assumed that the transformer is working at full load just before the overload is produced, which is the most unfavorable situation, and that the ambient temperature is 300 K. As the study is time-dependent, the simulations have been conducted in transient regime with time steps in the range between 0.5 and 5 s, depending on each particular case. From this set of simulations, a series of intensity/failure time values has been obtained, and a relationship between a continuous domain of intensities and failure times has been derived.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Thermal and flow fields of the transformer working at full load and at an ambient temperature of 300 K

Fig. 5 shows the temperature field obtained from the simulation of the transformer and its surroundings when it is working at full load, $S = 10$ kVA, and at an ambient temperature of 300 K. As it may be observed, the temperature is non-uniformly distributed along the transformer. In every winding limb, the maximum temperature is always found at the low tension winding placed at the highest point. In addition, in every winding there is a relative maximum temperature. These maxima are located at the copper parts, the places where heat sources arise. The highest temperatures are found in the limb with the windings nearer to the symmetry axis. More specifically, the hottest spot (454.65 K) appears at the middle point of the top-placed low-tension winding, as shown in Fig. 6. In the rest of windings, other relative maxima may be found, with decreasing values as the distance from the hottest spot increases. From these maximum values, the temperature decreases inside the transformer domain due to heat transmission by natural convection to the surrounding air at 300 K. The temperature minima in the transformer domain, as depicted in Fig. 5, are found on the surfaces in contact with the air.

Fig. 7 represents the temperature profile along the transformer surface in contact with the air, which is defined by the loop A-H in Fig. 6. On the transformer vertical surface D-E, the temperatures are higher in the zones between windings than on the windings themselves, due to the fact that in these zones there is no effective air circulation and heat transfer is thus hindered. The local values

Figure 5: Temperature field in the simulated domain.

of the heat transfer coefficient for the whole transformer surface A-H are presented in Fig. 8. Logically, the minimum values of the heat transfer coefficient are coincident with the transformer temperature maxima. The reason for this behavior is that, in the regions between windings in contact with the air, the air velocity is too small and the heat extraction capacity is thus lowered.

Finally, inside the air fluid domain shown in Fig. 5, two subdomains may be observed. The first one maintains the ambient temperature, i.e., is not affected by the transformer and is therefore outside the thermal boundary layer. The second one presents a temperature field with lower values as the distance from the transformer surface increases, i.e., it is inside the thermal boundary layer.

All the commented results meet natural convection premises: existence of a thermal boundary layer and existence of relative and absolute maxima in heat source regions. In addition, they also agree with the observed heating in transformers, with the highest temperatures reached at the most interior and top-placed windings [21].

In order to verify the conservation of energy, it must be checked that the heat flux generated in the transformer equals the heat flux evacuated by its surfaces in contact with the air. The heat generation and dissipation values are shown in Fig. 6, alongside the hot spots. As it may be observed, there is a small difference between the incoming and outgoing heat fluxes. Nevertheless, the magnitude of this difference is lower than the 10% of the total flux value and can be attributed to the integration performed in order to obtain the values of the evacuated heat flux. Thus, it can be concluded that the energy conservation

Figure 6: Hot spots and heat flux balance in the transformer.

Figure 7: Temperature profile along the transformer surface.

premise is fulfilled and the CFD is valid regarding energy calculations.

The assumption of natural convection as the main heat transfer mechanism must be also validated. With this purpose, the heat evacuated from the transformer vertical surface, 256.8 W/m, was used to calculate the mean surface temperature via integral methods, comparing the result with the temperature obtained by Fluent[®]. The mean temperature calculated by integral methods, 423.86 K, is very similar to the result obtained by Fluent[®], 421.59 K. Therefore, it can be concluded that natural convection laws are verified in the model. Both mean

Figure 8: Heat transfer coefficient along the transformer surface.

Figure 9: Air velocity field in the simulated domain.

temperatures have been plotted in Fig. 7.

Regarding the fluid velocity field, shown in Fig. 9, two clearly distinguishable domains separated by the momentum boundary layer may be observed: outside the boundary layer, the transformer has no effect and the flow remains quiescent; whereas inside this boundary layer, the flow field is vortical, with a large recirculating cell that enables heat transfer by natural convection.

The last hypothesis that required validation was the laminar flow assumption. The surface height that would cause transition to turbulent flow was calculated, obtaining a value of $H_{crit} = 0.497$ m. As the total transformer vertical height is 0.4 m, this result confirms that the flow inside the boundary layer remains in laminar state.

Fig. 10 shows the fluid vorticity field, which is related to the tendency of the

Figure 10: Air vorticity contours with thermal (TBL) and momentum (MBL) boundary layers.

fluid to rotate. As fluid rotation implies fluid mixing, the regions with higher vorticity values will logically correspond to the regions with higher heat transmission coefficient. This may be verified by comparing Fig. 10 and Fig. 8, as another proof of the coupling between the thermal and flow fields. Finally, the momentum and thermal boundary layers are approximately of the same size, as depicted in Fig. 10 (air at atmospheric conditions presents a Prandtl number close to unity, $Pr=0.71$).

3.2. Assessment of the lifespan of the transformer

The lifespan of the transformer is directly affected by its hot spot temperature. Fig. 11 shows the maximum temperatures reached in the transformer for 8 values of the transformer working power at the four tested ambient temperatures.

By the application of the least squares method, the following polynomial function has been obtained, which relates the transformer hot spot temperature to its working regime and the ambient temperature:

$$T_{HS} = 317.6292 - 0.6389 T_{\infty} - 9.9863 S + \dots \quad (23)$$

$$\dots + 0.0336 T_{\infty} S + 0.0025 T_{\infty}^2 + 0.9970 S^2$$

In an attempt to generalize this equation for other working conditions, 6 additional simulations have been performed for ambient temperatures outside the range used for the fitting (280 and 330 K). The difference between the results of the simulations and the polynomial equation is less than 3 K (1% of the total temperature), so Equation 23 may be also employed for extrapolation. These

Figure 11: Transformer hot spot temperatures as a function of working load and ambient temperature (Fluent[®] data – squares; mathematical approximations – lines).

simulated results, as well as the equation extrapolation, are included in Figure 11.

Finally, the lifespan of the transformer may be obtained coupling Equation 23 and Equation 21, which links the useful life of the transformer with its hot spot temperature. Using Equation 21, the failure time at nominal working conditions for this transformer is around 110,000 h. This value has been found to be consistent with typical values found in the literature [5],[6],[13],[21],[23]. Thanks to this tool, a continuous management of the transformer during its useful life is possible, avoiding the placement of thermocouples inside the transformer.

3.3. Assessment of the intensity-failure time relationship under an overload situation

The results obtained from the transient analysis of the temperature rise in the transformer under 9 different overload values are represented in Fig. 12. This figure shows the time span between the initial state of the transformer (full load working regime and ambient temperature of 300 K) and the time when the threshold temperature of the insulation is reached (250°C).

With these results, a relationship between the failure time and a continuous range of overload intensity values has been obtained by least squares method:

$$\ln t_F = 11.73/I_R + 3.996 - 0.2282I_R + 0.008919I_R^2 \quad (24)$$

where t_F is the failure time in seconds and I_R is the ratio between the overload intensity and the nominal intensity. In order for a transformer protection to be suitable, it will be required to possess a $t_F - I_R$ characteristic curve lower than the transformer one.

Finally, Fig. 13 represents the evolution of the transformer hot spot temperature, starting from the same initial conditions defined above, when an overload twice larger than nominal intensity is produced. For this particular case, the transformer insulation is able to withstand the overload during a time of around 3.9 hours.

Figure 12: Failure time depending on the overload intensity/nominal intensity ratio (Fluent[®] data – squares; mathematical approximation – line).

Figure 13: Hot spot temperature evolution for an overload twice larger than nominal intensity.

4. Conclusion

The safe working limits of a 10 kVA dry-type transformer with H-class insulation have been analyzed using the CFD software Fluent[®]. The developed numerical model is able to predict the thermal and fluid fields generated by the transformer, providing a better insight into the transformer heat transmission mechanisms and helping to develop more efficient maintenance plans.

All the assumptions made for the development of the numerical model have been verified. Firstly, the total energy of the system is conserved. Secondly, the hypothesis of natural convection as the main heat transfer mechanism has been validated, with a difference of only 2 K between the numerical result and the result from the analysis via experimental correlations. Thirdly, the laminar flow assumption has been verified as the transformer height, 0.4 m, does not exceed the turbulent transition critical value, 0.497 m. It is also worth highlighting that the thermal and momentum boundary layer sizes are consistent with the behavior expected for air. Finally, the hot spot and temperature distributions are coincident with experimental observations in transformers [21]: there are absolute and relative temperature maxima at the transformer windings, with the highest temperatures found at the most interior and top-placed ones.

The coupling between the thermal and flow fields is worth noticing, as the flow is driven by buoyancy forces which arise as a result of air density variations due to air temperature changes. Reciprocally, changes in the flow field affect the heat flux from the transformer and thus modify the thermal field.

Regarding the most practical results from this study, two sets of simulations have been performed. From the first set of 32 simulations, a relationship between the transformer hot spot temperature, its load level and the ambient temperature has been obtained. This enables the estimation of the hot spot temperature with just a thermometer and an ammeter, a method much simpler than the installation of a thermocouple at the transformer hot spot. With the predicted hot spot temperature, the loss of the transformer useful life may be estimated using an experimental relationship. The predicted lifespan of the transformer has been calculated (111,000 hours), being in accordance with other studies and existing experimental data [5],[6],[13],[21],[23]. This simulation approach is very useful to optimize the transformer working conditions, as well as to perform amortization studies of the machine.

In the second set of 9 scenarios, the time that the system resists an overload before reaching the insulating failure temperature has been predicted. As this time depends on the overload intensity, these predictions make easier to select an appropriate protection system for the transformer.

The results of this study confirm the great value of numerical simulations for the failure mode evaluation of dry-type transformers [1], which describe winding insulation failure as the main failure mode. However, the laminar flow assumption must be taken with care when generalizing the results of this work to bigger transformers, as the transformer critical height could be then exceeded. Future studies with 3D simulations, including border and turbulence effects in the fluid behavior, could help to identify the impact of secondary effects on the accuracy of the numerical predictions. Finally, two possible improvements to the model could be the introduction of temperature-dependent materials in the calculations and the simulation of the magnetic flux inside the core region.

To summarize, an insight into the thermal and flow fields generated by a working dry-type transformer has been provided by this work. This may help to develop preventive and maintenance plans for transformer systems, while reducing the need for instrumentation and experimental testing.

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Highlights

- A numerical model for heat transfer in dry-type power transformers is proposed.
- Thermal and flow fields generated by natural convection are accurately predicted.
- Hot spot temperature and location under different working conditions are provided.
- A relationship for the calculation of the hot spot temperature is derived.
- Failure time of the transformer is given as a function of the overload value.

ACCEPTED MANUSCRIPT